

УДК 656.073.7

ОСОБЕННОСТИ ТАМОЖЕННОЙ ЛОГИСТИКИ В СЛУЧАЕ ТРАНСПОРТИРОВКИ В ОГРАНИЧЕННОМ ПРОСТРАНСТВЕ И ВРЕМЕНИ

PECULIARITIES OF CUSTOMS LOGISTICS IN THE CASE OF TRANSPORTATION IN THE LIMITED SPACE AND TIME

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Аннотация. В современных условиях транспортные процессы включает в себя не только транспортировку товаров от поставщиков к потребителям, но и большой объем экспедиторских, информационных, таможенных и транзакционных операций по обработке, страхованию, хранению и т. д. перевозимых товаров.

Транспортный процесс сталкивается с особыми трудностями, если он ограничен областью пограничного таможенного оформления нескольких государств в ограниченное время и пространство.

Внедрение современных принципов таможенной логистики в практике таможенного оформления транспорта и грузов в ограниченное время и пространство позволит нам значительно повысить организационно-экономическую устойчивость транспортных процессов.

В статье обсуждаются тенденции использования таможенной логистики для упрощения процедур таможенного оформления транспортных средств и товаров в случае прохождения транспортных процессов в ограниченное время и в пространстве.

Abstract. In modern conditions, transport processes encompass not only the movement of goods from suppliers to consumers, but also a large amount of forwarding, information, customs and transactional processing operations on insurance, storage of transported goods.

Transport process faces special difficulties, if it is restricted by the scope of border and customs procedures of several countries in the limited space and time.

Implementation of modern principles of customs logistics in the practice of customs clearance of transport and goods in the limited space and time will allow us for improving significantly the organizational and economic sustainability of transport processes.

The paper examines the trends in the use of customs logistics to simplify customs clearance of vehicles and goods in the case of transportation in the limited space and time.

Ключевые слова: перевозка грузов, таможенная логистика, таможенное оформление.

Keywords: carriage of goods; customs logistics; limited space and time.

The role and function of Georgia as a transit country are growing with every passing day. This is conditioned by its significant geostrategic position and implementation of large-scale transit projects. In addition, a rational and effective use of geostrategic position is one of the major bases of country's further economic development.

During the movement through the territory of Georgia, transit cargo cross the customs posts and border crosses of at least four countries in a short time, and they undergo customs procedures in compliance with the legislation of these countries. The realization of these prospects largely depends on the activities of the country's customs administration. The introduction of high-quality customs services, the application of the effective innovative technologies in customs treatment and customs control are the most important characteristics of customs operations. That is why more attention should be given to studying the experience of using methods of logistics in the organization of customs treatment and customs control.

Along with a well-organized road infrastructure and other factors, the main basis for the country's transit development is also represented by simple customs procedures. But the simplicity of customs procedures is conditioned by the harmonized customs legislation and a small number of barriers to border-crossing.

In terms of the formation and development of transport and logistics system in Georgia, it is possible to note the lack of use of logistics approach to implementation of customs operations, since only some logistic functions are implemented to reduce costs in the process of moving goods across the customs border. The customs authorities of Georgia, until recently, as the main function, have been tailored to address fiscal and law enforcement tasks. At the same time, the natural evolution of customs requires technological improvement of customs clearance and customs control. As one of the most important indicators of the efficiency of the customs system is minimizing the amount of time required for the performance of customs formalities. After all, the main consequence of delays of goods at the border is raising their prices within the country, in the case of imported goods, and the loss of transit flows, if goods are delayed in third countries [1].

The essence of goods distribution consists in a combination of physical and economic processes. Physical movement lies in its territorial movement from one geographical location to another. The choice of transport mode is essential here, as well as the current state of transport and

customs infrastructure promoting the realization of the potential of individual modes of transport and efficient use of multimodal transport. Movement in the economic area consists in the transfer of rights to use, possess and control the goods from one owner and user, to another owner. Both aspects are not only in interest of a private international law, but also of customs legislation, on the basis of which it is possible to make conclusion on a significant impact of economic and legal factors on customs logistics [2].

In addition to customs legislation, the border crossing procedures are also regulated by the international treaties, different laws and instructions. Given the view that border crossings are governed by quite numerous normative instruments, of vital importance is the further simplification of transit-related procedures for any person crossing the border. The simplification of transit-related customs procedures will greatly assist those persons crossing the border, who move from one country to another through Georgia and are engaged in the international carriage.

The further simplification (or the complete elimination) of transit-related customs procedures gathered in a limited period of time and in a limited area, must be based on the international treaties of Georgia, a new Customs Code and the relevant secondary legislation, as well as on other Georgian legislation in force and information received from State institutions.

Crossing the customs border of Georgia is allowed in the previously designated places (during working hours, from 9.00 a.m. to 6.00 p.m. in all customs posts, except “Tsiteli Khidi”, “Sadakhlo”, “Gardabani”, “Akhkerpi”, “Guguti”, “Mtkvari”, “Lagodekhi”, “Samtatskaro”, “Kazbegi”, “Vale”, “Ninotsminda”, “Tbilisi Airport”, “Sarpi”, “Senaki Airport”, “Batumi Port” and “Poti Port”, where the working time is 24 hours). Crossing the border in other places or with goods and vehicles during outside working hours of customs authorities is allowed with written from the Customs Department.

There are five vehicle customs checkpoints and one railway checkpoint on the border strip between Georgia and Armenia; seven vehicle customs checkpoints and one railway checkpoint are established on the border between Georgia and Azerbaijan; two vehicle customs checkpoints and two railway checkpoints are established on the border between Georgia and Turkey; and in all four vehicle customs checkpoints and one railway checkpoint are established on the border between Georgia and Russia, of which only one – Kazbegi (Zemo Larsi) vehicle checkpoint is currently acting, but operation of others has been temporarily suspended.

The main transit cargo flows transported by vehicles through Georgia move mostly: from Turkey to Azerbaijan, and then to countries in Central Asia and back; to Armenia and Russia and back. But the carriage of goods by railway transport is mostly carried out from the Black Sea ports of Georgia to Armenia, Azerbaijan and countries in Central Asia, and back. Also, transportation of crude oil is carried out from Kazakhstan to Azerbaijan through the sea ports of Georgia.

The issue of activating cargo transportation from China to European countries on the newly-open Tbilisi-Karsi railway section and through the Black Sea ports of Georgia (including the deep-sea Anaklia port under construction), is still under consideration at the governmental level.

The distance between the individual customs checkpoints hesitates between 150 and 300 km, and in the case of the well-organized road conditions, the loaded vehicle covers this distance in 4-8 hours on average. The predicted further growth of transit cargo flows, and the establishment of close relations with customs services in neighboring transit countries create the conditions for the further simplification of customs procedures.

The simplification of procedures of trade and transport services is in close relationship and mutual influence with the general economic level of country's development. Most of the measures to simplify customs procedures, directly affect the effectiveness of both external and internal trade of the country, have an impact on the overall state of the human capital of the country, its legal framework infrastructure and the use of information technology.

Table 1 provides information on the number of transit vehicles moving through the territory of Georgia by year (www.economy.ge).

As Table illustrates, ground transportation has a largest share, and reducing the time for procedures of customs clearance through the implementation of the principles of customs logistics in the organization of border crossings will have a significant economic impact on reducing the total transport times.

Logistic approach to the management of export-import trade flows is fundamentally different from the traditional order that builds an optimally organized system of interaction of all participants of transport process in the implementation of customs procedures to maximize the aggregate economic effect. It is obvious that the specificity of the international logistics chains is that not everything depends on the participants of process. Clearly, the certain significant operations are performed by the national customs authorities, whose purposes may both coincide and be contrary to objectives of the participants of transport process. So, the essence of the integrated logistics management approach to the transit cargo flow processes consists also in the establishment of a system, the principle of which is the optimization of the time and financial costs for procedures associated with rapid movement of goods across the customs border, and with their subsequent timely involvement in economic activities in the interests of all participants in the international transport processes and transit country too.

Table.

THE NUMBER OF TRANSIT VEHICLES

<i>Mode of transport</i>	<i>2013</i>	<i>2014</i>	<i>2015</i>	<i>2016</i>	<i>2017 (2 months)</i>
Maritime	39.0	75.0	85.0	41.0	33.0
Railway	19 740.0	20 434.0	12 923.0	13 877.0	2 875.0
Road transport	142 547.0	156 006.0	151 584.0	164 230.0	29 054.0
Total	162 326.0	176 515.0	164 592.0	178 148.0	31 962.0

The use of logistic approaches in the process of regulating the export-import commodity flows results in the creation of a logistics system in the field of international trade, as well as in their effective maintenance. Among those peculiarities, which differ the logistics and transport systems, the emphasis should be placed on the following ones:

1. Logisticization of customs clearance and customs control of commodity flows should be carried out taking into consideration of interlinkages with the large logistics systems of international trade, which include the customs systems and have common purposes.

2. The project of the transport and logistics system should be assessed in accordance with costs incurred or the extent of the deviation from the optimal customs modes.

3. The optimal project of the transport and logistics system cannot be created only by the fragmentary implementation of changes in customs clearance and customs control of commodity flows. It must be based on managerial activities, which will be expedient for all participants of foreign economic activities.

4. The process of customs clearance and customs control of commodity flows must be carried out purposefully and continuously. To that end, in the process of the operation of the customs-logistics system, it is necessary to detect and eliminate all negative results.

All this demonstrates that it is necessary to create logistical mechanism for management of all fields of international trade, which will provide the effective functioning of a macro-logistics system of customs matters in the country.

The simplification of customs procedures and reduction in the time of customs operations must be accompanied by the improvements in the effectiveness of law enforcement and anti-corruption activities of the customs service. Customs logistics is intended for addressing complex challenges and is aimed at making the import-export processes most optimal and cost-effective. Let's give an example of the possible simplification of phytosanitary measures: in order to reduce the time required for clearance of goods subject to phytosanitary measures, we consider it appropriate to undertake measures as follows:

1. It is necessary to change approach to clearance of goods, and provide on-site clearance of the single- or multi-code simple clearance goods in the clearance economic zone (CEZ) without transferring the documentation, that is, the functions of CEZ must be coordinated with the functions of the border.
2. To place one or two operators on the object of border crossing existing within the territory of CEZ, with appropriate computer software.
3. To develop a software module, which will simplify customs clearance of goods subject to phytosanitary measures, by displaying the basic product information, and of course, by payment of customs duties provided for in legislation.

As noted above, the customs procedures are carried out in CEZ. According to a new approach, the clearance of goods after phytosanitary measures must be carried out on site. More particularly, upon completion of a documentary audit, these documents must be handed to the operators located at the same object, who will provide the clearance of goods in a simplified declaration form, after their passing through the green route. This will significantly reduce the time required for the clearance of goods, and in a number of cases, filer costs as well, since there are many cases of the facts, when the owners of the goods have to carry out the clearance outside working hours that doubles the cost of services.

We believe that this will contribute to the reduction in time required for the clearance of goods that will positively impact on the movement of goods and will contribute to the transit development.

Ensuring competitiveness and sustainability of Georgia's transit corridor calls for great efforts. It is necessary to improve the quality of transit infrastructure. The status of the "attractive transport corridor" is a guarantee for the sustainability of the South Caucasus region, which implies investment promotion and the creation of the stable prerequisites for bringing resources onto the global market. This requires the modernized communication systems, as well as the improved tariff, legal and banking systems. The situation typical of a small country, which means that they play the so-called role of buffer, has been recently changed by the completely different international relations. This is the performance and development of a transit function, which is clearly a substantive leverage for involving these countries in the world's business processes, as well as for further economic growth.

Funding: This work was supported by Shota Rustaveli Georgian National Science Foundation (SRNSFG) [DP 2016_5. Organization and management of transport processes].

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*Работа поступила
в редакцию 12.12.2017 г.*

*Принята к публикации
16.12.2017 г.*

Ссылка для цитирования:

Kochadze T., Mamuladze R., Sharabidze D., Gudadze A. Peculiarities of customs logistics in the case of transportation in the limited space and time // Бюллетень науки и практики. Электрон. журн. 2018. Т. 4. №1. С. 154-159. Режим доступа: <http://www.bulletennauki.com/kochadze-mamuladze> (дата обращения 15.01.2018).

Cite as (APA):

Kochadze, T., Mamuladze, R., Sharabidze, D., & Gudadze, A. (2018). Peculiarities of customs logistics in the case of transportation in the limited space and time. *Bulletin of Science and Practice*, 4, (1), 154-159